

AI4Media Results in Brief: **Key societal concerns of AI applications in Media**

Authors:

Anna Schjøtt Hansen, Natali Helberger
Tobias Blanke (University of Amsterdam),
and Rasa Bočytė (Netherlands Institute for
Sound & Vision)

This factsheet presents six societal concerns of AI applications that affect or impact the media industry and presents core points of consideration for the media industry, policy makers and AI researchers who engage with the media sector.

This information derived from the research and literature review conducted by AI4Media led by University of Amsterdam, and it is available in detail in the document "Initial white paper on the social, economic, and political impact of media AI technologies" [here](#).

Societal Concern #1

Biases and discrimination

AI is on one hand discussed as a potential solution to mitigating existing media biases (e.g., overrepresentation of male sources). On the other hand, AI systems can sustain and further amplify existing biases (e.g., in content moderation where minorities are less protected from hate speech). This will lead to severe long-term effects on the role of media in society and the democratic practices it cultivates.

Key areas of action

Upskilling

More domain-specific, social and/or cultural expertise in the development process of AI systems for media

Collaboration . Upskilling

Foster support, tools, and resources for responsible AI practices in the media sector

Interdisciplinary Research . Collaboration

New best practices on how to produce just AI systems in the media sector

Policy

Regulation that promotes and fosters responsible AI practices in the media sector, rather than attempt to constrain the use

Infrastructure

Domain-specific, open-source and non-commercial datasets for training AI systems

Societal Concern #2

Media (in)dependence and commercialisation

The platformisation of society also applies to the media sector, who are dependent on e.g., social media in their distribution of content and entangled in commercial data infrastructures, as well as commercial vendors of AI solutions. **One major concern regarding this commercialisation and dependence on different platforms is the effects of such dependencies on the media independence.**

Key areas of action

Infrastructure

Responsible, domain-specific infrastructures to support responsible AI practices

Collaboration . Infrastructure . Policy

More engagement with media asset management (MAMs) vendors in the audio-visual sector

Policy . Interdisciplinary Research

Best practices and policies of 'diversity by design'

Communication . Interdisciplinary Research

Critical awareness of economic 'patrons' of the media sector and how they affect the development in the media sector

Funding

Funding schemes oriented in EU values

Societal Concern #3

Inequalities in access to AI

While the use of AI is expanding rapidly, it is not doing so equally across the world and the primary benefactors of AI solution remains the global north and particularly English-speaking countries. Inequality in access is, therefore, also a major concern. In the media sector this is also further widening the existing competitiveness divide between smaller and larger media organisations, which puts media diversity at risk.

Key areas of action

Funding

Funding schemes and initiatives focusing on media diversity

Interdisciplinary Research . Policy

Increased focus on global AI divides and their consequences

Infrastructure

Developing of AI models for diverse languages or adaptive models

Societal Concern #4

Labour displacements, monitoring, and professional control

AI is often discussed in terms of the risk of labour displacement. In the media sector the effects of AI on existing jobs remain limited, although some examples of displacement are emerging. AI also induces new power asymmetries between employees and employers as metrics and monitoring practices are becoming more common. Last, AI is transforming existing media practices (e.g., genres and formats) and challenging the professional control and oversight of both production and distribution practices.

Key areas of action

Interdisciplinary Research . Policy

More research and policies addressing potential displacement patterns resulting from AI

Upskilling . Education

Increased focus on data and AI in media education

Infrastructure . Communication

Tools or methods for meaningful oversight for media professionals

Interdisciplinary Research

More research on how AI is changing labour conditions and growing power asymmetries in the media sector

Societal Concern #5

Privacy, transparency, accountability and liability

The privacy discussion regarding AI for media relate mostly to data privacy, where the conflict between commercial and democratic ideals intersects. Media organisations must consider their responsibility regarding data privacy models and new best practices of responsible data practices are needed. The transparency discussion is currently focused on the practices of disclosure that media organisations currently employ and how streamlining is needed to ensure better transparency in the media landscape. Accountability is mainly discussed in relation to how and where to place responsibility as new actors enter the media landscape with the use of AI (e.g., service providers of AI).

Key areas of action

**Collaboration .
Interdisciplinary
Research**

More best practices of responsible data practices in the media sector

**Collaboration .
Interdisciplinary
Research . Policy**

Best practices and policies regarding disclosure of AI systems for the media sector

**Communication .
Infrastructure**

Explainable and transparent AI solutions that can help users understand how AI systems work and makes decision

Policy

Clearer regulation and guidelines on the liability question regarding AI

Societal Concern #6

Manipulation and mis- and disinformation as an institutional threat

The threat of manipulation is highly present in the discussion of AI and media as well as in society as large through concepts such as 'fake news'. In the media sector specifically, much discussion centre on how other actors through the manipulation of content (e.g., deep fakes) or by affecting modes of distribution (e.g., bots) can manipulate the public opinion. As media continue to serve and important role in society as trusted sources of information, the negative effects this might have on the trustworthiness of media is significant. As a core actor in the fight against disinformation, the development of tools to support the work of media professionals is important.

Key areas of action

Infrastructure

Mitigative and adaptive AI systems to counteract misinformation

Interdisciplinary Research . Policy

More transparency in moderation systems and AI fact checking systems

Communication . Interdisciplinary Research

More knowledge on fact checking as a social practice and its effects in the deliberate landscape